

The Global Digital Congress

(Extended ChatGPT Version)

Abstract: The concept I've described, envisions a highly advanced form of direct democracy facilitated by a global quantum internet. Here's a breakdown of its key characteristics:

Period of Time: The initiative spans from the 23rd to the 24th century, initially operating as a partial direct democracy and evolving into a total direct democracy by the 4th millennium.

Geographical Area: It covers the entire globe, making it a worldwide initiative.

Aim: The primary goal is to establish a system of global direct democracy, allowing all citizens of the world to directly participate in the legislative process.

Technology: It relies on a highly advanced form of communication infrastructure known as the Global Quantum Internet. Quantum internet technology offers unparalleled security and efficiency in data transmission and processing.

Number of Congressmen Connected: The system aims to connect billions of individuals, effectively enabling vast participation in the decision-making process.

Purpose: The main purpose is to empower citizens by allowing them to vote directly on legislative bills through the internet, thereby eliminating intermediaries and enhancing democratic participation.

Conclusion: This vision reflects a futuristic and ambitious approach to governance, leveraging cutting-edge technology to achieve unprecedented levels of democratic engagement and inclusion.

Note: This manuscript was written with the help of ChatGPT

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